

Mathematics education in middle schools of Ethiopia: Culture and language in the textbook

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In this paper I present a study of mathematics education in middle schools of Ethiopia, focusing on the textbook. Particularly, I examine how textbook is connecting mathematics education with the local culture. I also set out about the use of the local language in mathematics education. The study draws on cultural historical activity theory. The analysis reveals that the textbook has limitations in connecting mathematics with the local culture. Their limitations appear to be consequences of the education policy of the country. The implications for cultural and linguistic issues in mathematics education in Ethiopia and beyond are set out.

Introduction

This paper reports an examination of mathematics education in primary schools of Ethiopia with particular focus on how textbook is connecting mathematics education with the local culture and the use of the local language in mathematics education.

There have been studies, which expose about mathematics education and making cultural connection (e.g., Fyhn, et al., 2017; Jannok Nutti, 2013; Lipka & Adams, 2004). Jannok Nutti explored and exposed the mathematical activities in handcrafters and reindeer herders of Sámi people in Sweden, where she analyzed their stories based on the six activities proposed by Bishop (1988). Jannok Nutti expressed concerns about the in-availability of resources for designing and developing a mathematics education which is based on indigenous culture (e.g., Jannok Nutti, 2013). Sámi mathematics education has long been struggling to move from boarding schools, where children were isolated from their culture, to establishing a school situation where children are encouraged to build on their cultural heritage (ibid).

There are many factors for not getting the opportunity to learn mathematics of students' own culture. Jannok Nutti (2013) mentions that some of the factors are the dialect used in the textbook; the teachers' opinions about what works best for succeeding in the national examination, and that the textbooks are mere translations of the national textbooks with hardly any values of the communities. Moreover, time constraint and constraints in teachers' knowledge of teaching mathematics, which is based on the indigenous culture, can contribute to limiting the opportunity.

Please cite as: Gebremichael, A. T. (2021). Mathematics education in middle schools of Ethiopia: Culture and language in the textbook. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 455–466). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5414006>

There have been efforts to produce teaching materials through a collaboration of teachers and researchers (e.g., Fyhn et al., 2017). Fyhn et al. (2017) reported results of investigation of Sámi braiding where they explored ways of using it in teaching discrete mathematics at Sámi middle schools. They participated in exploring cultural artifacts and designed tasks based on their exploration (Fyhn et al., 2017). The Fyhn group stresses that the starting point is not the standard mathematics but, the Sámi culture. The issue of tension between Western traditions as reflected in the standard mathematics and Sámi traditions is also revealed. Fyhn et al. (2017) interpreted the Sámi descriptions used in braiding corresponding to words down/up, below/above and right/left as 3-dimensional space. Their results show that investigations of Sámi braiding can be utilized in connection with students' learning of variables based on numbers. It can also be used in the teaching of combinatorics.

Lipka and Adams (2004) reported their study about mathematics curriculum, which was based on the culture and implemented in Indigenous people of Alaska, USA. They examined the mathematics of Yup'ik Eskimo in Alaska. The authors mention the uniqueness of this Indigenous community's counting and quantifying ways and systems. Their study indicate that it is vital to involve the local community particularly elders in the development of mathematics curriculum for Indigenous people (e.g., Lipka & Adams, 2004). Lipka and Adams (2004) suggest starting with students own experiences in Indigenous community and challenging students to come up with their own conjectures and their own evidence for the conjectures they have made.

There are studies, exploring and exposing mathematics used in Africa, which are important for providing culturally connected mathematics education (e.g., Gerdes, 2014). According to Gerdes, diverse mathematics concepts and themes can be taught in African schools using African cultural activities and artifacts as a starting point. Gerdes provides an example where the use of geometry by Mozambican artisans in weaving of traditional basket can be utilized in teaching geometry.

On the other hand, there are studies examining the problem in learning mathematics in a foreign language (e.g., Setati, 2005). In her research project about learning mathematics in primary schools in South Africa, Setati (2005) examines the complex relationship language and mathematics learning. She stresses that mastery of mathematics' language is part of its learning. According to Setati (2005), language as a tool is both cultural and political. It not only is used to communicate thoughts but also creates aspects of who we are (ibid).

In a report about students learning by participating in practical activities, Miettinen (1999) stresses that better learning can occur when students participate in the actual out-of-school activities than through obtaining information about those activities in the classroom. He makes distinction between interest in a topic and motivation for the sake of succeeding. Contrary to the practice in the schooling activity, in enhancing better learning, interest in the topic is more important than the motivation to succeed (ibid). Consistent with Miettinen, the current study draws on cultural historical activity theory, and attempts to expose the activities which the Ethiopian textbook focuses on as well as to expose the potential influence of the textbook on the school mathematics.

Some studies of mathematics education in Ethiopia over the past decades at least mentioned issues of connection of mathematics with Ethiopian situation (e.g., Dutton, 1968). Traditional games, and other activities in Ethiopian culture involving mathematics are also documented in earlier studies (ibid), which have survived to this day. In another study, upper secondary students named several activities in Ethiopian culture, which involve mathematics (Gebremichael et al., 2011). In the current study, I attempt to answer the research question: How does textbook attempt to connect mathematics education with the local culture and utilize the local language.

This paper is structured as follows. This introduction section is followed by the remaining sections, which are presented in this order: activity theory, methods, and the data presentation and analysis. Then, I set out the discussion and conclusion.

Activity theory

I adopt cultural historical activity theory (CHAT) as a theoretical perspective to analyze the data. I examine the textbook in search of suggestion of activities, which are culturally and historically situated in Ethiopia. I also attempt to expose the other activities in Ethiopia.

Following Leont'ev (1979), I understand activity as being vital to human life. Activity has various components primarily the acting subject interacts with the object of the activity (ibid). This interaction is mediated by mediating instruments. The remaining components are division of labor, rules, and community (ibid). Human beings participate in activities and activities are historically situated (ibid). The Ethiopian traditional activities are historically situated in the culture even before the mathematics textbook and the schooling activity, as we know it now, were introduced in the country (Wagaw, 1979). In the current study, schooling is considered as an activity and learning mathematics is a goal directed action mediated by instruments as part of schooling.

When I examine the textbook, I search for suggestions of activities. The textbook is an instrument for the learning of mathematics. It mediates the interaction between the student and the goal of mathematics learning and the motive of schooling as well as between the student and the teacher. The teacher's guide suggests that teachers should use the textbook for preparing the lesson and in teaching. The teacher gives exercises to the student from the textbook. The exercises in the textbook help the student in acquiring mathematics knowledge and prepares the student to succeed in the examinations. The textbook also describes the division of labor by providing what the student should do as part of the learning process. It also describes the rules/norms of the mathematics classroom by letting the student do the exercises as homework before coming to class and as classwork while obtaining help from the teacher. The textbook also provides the student with suggestions of solutions for the exercises. The textbook may also determine the community by providing a suggestion of working in groups.

The school has rules, division of labor and tools. Teachers and administration are parts of the school communities. In the mathematics classroom, the object of the activity includes the goals and motives of the school. The goals of engaging the child in the process is

transferring mathematical knowledge. The school has a motive of producing students who can succeed in moving over to the next level by succeeding in the examinations. The outcomes of the activity are children with mathematics knowledge, skill and competence, possibly enabling the child to succeed in examinations.

Methods

I employ document analysis because it fits my purpose of examining and exposing the cultural issues as described in the textbook and the teacher's guide. This is consistent with the purpose method as set out by Bowen (2009). According to Bowen one purpose of document analysis is extracting information from a relevant resource. The data in this study is the texts in the textbook and the teacher's guide as well as in the policy document. The purpose in the current study is to expose how the textbook connects mathematics education with the cultural heritages of the Ethiopian society. The research method which fits to this investigation is document analysis method.

In examining the textbook, I first, explore the structure of the textbook as well as the chapters. Then, I examine the textbook in search of texts, which mention the available activities in Ethiopian culture and society including the schooling activity, and I code them. In the third step I summarize the available activities into groups. In the fourth step, I examine those activities to expose the components of the activities such as the instruments, communities, rules, and the division of labor, which I set out in the theoretical perspective section. I examine the level of detail about the exposition of the activities and the approach suggested with respect to their favorability to learning. I follow the same steps in examining the teacher's guide. Then, I merge my results from the two sources in the presentation of results. I also re-examine them, and cross-check when required. Some text in the policy document is also examined and extracted.

The data presentation and analysis

In this section, I set out the data and the analysis. the data in this study is the texts in the textbook and teacher's guide. I start with presenting the topics in the textbook 6-grade textbook. The section has four subsections, which are presented in this order: policy issues; the textbook and language issues; making connection with out-of-school activities and a further look at activities.

Policy issues

The ministry of education is the responsible organ for implementing the education policy (MoE, 1994). The policy document, MoE (1994) hardly has direction about the local culture. In its introduction, it mentions *culture* in connection with building culture of problem solving. The policy document has general and specific objectives. The general objectives, among others, focus on problem solving skills and creativity. It also states culture in connection with democracy, namely, about building culture of democracy. Ethiopia has diverse cultures and languages. The policy document states that one of the specific objectives

is ensuring that people will use their languages in education. On the other hand, there are no such statements about their culture.

As part of its strategy, the policy document has general statements about curriculum. It states that it intends ensuring development of curriculum and preparation of textbook, which maintain international standards while paying proper consideration to regional (local) circumstances and gender-related matters. However, it is not clear what these regional circumstances are, and apart from the attention given to the regional languages, the cultural issues are not specifically mentioned in the policy document. The education policy document mentions that one of its objectives is providing education which is secular. The Ethiopian people are largely religious. The country is home for Orthodox Christians and Muslims, which are the two largest religious groups, respectively. The apparent consequence for the textbook will be considered later in this section.

The textbook and language issues

The curriculum is designed centrally by the ministry of education. The ministry delegates the regional education bureaus to prepare textbook. The grade 6 textbook, which I examine, is written in local vernacular, Amharic (Ministry of Education of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2011a). The grade 6 teacher's guide is also written in Amharic (Ministry of Education of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2011b). Amharic is the official language of the country and has its own alphabets, which it shares with a very old Ethiopian language, Ge'ez. The textbook uses these alphabets as mathematical symbols such as variables and in naming sets.

At 6th grade, there is only one textbook. In general, the chapters of the textbook are structured in the same way, with little variation. The chapters start with stating the learning goals and contents of the chapter. This is followed by introductory words, which attempt to relate the topic with experiences, which the students are familiar with, or with their prior knowledge. Then, it provides the contents before, presenting proofs for some of the mathematical statements. The chapters end by providing a summary and key words followed by review exercises. The 6-grade textbook has six chapters. The following are the topics of the first four chapters, in this order: sets, composite numbers, fractions and whole numbers. Chapter 5 is a combination of topics. Its title is equations, inequalities, and proportionality. This chapter includes coordinate system and graphs. The final chapter is about geometry.

As mentioned earlier in this section, the textbook is written in the local language, Amharic. The mathematics terms are usually in Amharic. Some of the terms may be difficult for the student. The 6th grade textbook also provides description or definition of many terms. For example, in one of the three sections of Chapter 5, which is about coordinate system, the section starts with activity, and it provides description of terms later. The following text is an English translation of an excerpt from the first paragraph of the section:

Under this heading you learn about coordinate system. You also learn about how you can describe points as ordered pairs on the coordinate plane (Ministry of Education of the Federal

Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2011a, p. 123, author's translation, see Supplement 1 for original version in Amharic).

Following this excerpt, the textbook provides activity, where it provides a set of instructions to students, which includes asking to draw a coordinate system. Finally, it provides descriptions of most of the terms based on what the students would have done in the activity. However, there are some limitations in this regard. For example, the first instruction states, "draw two straight lines on your notebook." (Ministry of Education of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2011a, p. 123, author's translation, see Supplement 2 for original version in Amharic). The author had to struggle to find out what the Amharic phrase which corresponds to "straight line" means. This key term may not be familiar to the students. Absence of description of the term might affect their learning of this topic.

Making connections with out-of-school activities

The textbook gives examples and exercises, which make connections between mathematics and the out-of-school activities. For example, in the sixth-grade textbook, Chapter 5 provides an exercise in the topic *proportionality*, which asks students a series of questions such as comparing the amount and prices if the student buys something. Then, it provides answers to some of these questions. In the first chapter of the sixth-grade textbook, which is about sets, mentions of wildlife, a set of traditional dishes in a restaurant, etc. the traditional dishes are parts of the Ethiopian culture. Apart from such mentions, the textbook hardly provides examples or tasks of mathematics' connections with the local culture. There are hardly any mention of traditional activities, institutions, communities, or instruments or artifacts in the Ethiopian culture.

The teacher's guide provides detailed guidance about what the teacher should do in teaching every topic. It also encourages making connection with the out-of-school activities. For example, in the first chapter, which is about sets, it states:

Before providing definition of a set, explain to them those relating to the various examples given in the introduction of the chapter. Furthermore, these will help them to relate the sets they experience in their everyday life with those, which are available in mathematics. You can start your explanation with those which are locally available. You can start with the following: family [...] a class of students, a football team. [...] The example you give, and the concrete things should be clearly understandable to every student. Encourage them so that they can participate. Encourage them to give their own examples of sets which they find in their everyday life and in mathematics (Ministry of Education of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2011b, p. 3, author's translation, see Supplement 3 for original version in Amharic).

However, the list does not include peculiar activities, artifacts, communities in the cultures of Ethiopian society. It suggests such examples for the teaching of empty set, "a set of cats with 8 legs" (Ministry of Education of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2011b, p. 6, author's translation, see Supplement 4 for original version in Amharic). The teacher's guide provides further guidance. It states:

From the textbook let students discuss about [...] then, ask students to work on [...] from exercise 1.2 let students discuss about differences. (Ministry of Education of the Federal

Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2011b, p. 8, author's translation, see Supplement 5 for original version in Amharic)

Then it provides answers to the exercises: The answers to the exercises include: "group of students, group of hens, people who play football" (Ministry of Education of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2011b, p. 8, author's translation, see Supplement 5 for original version in Amharic). Moreover, the teacher's guide provides guidance about several issues such as students' motivation, building on students' answers, students' active participation and providing feedback. However, there is no such guidance about making cultural connections.

Like the chapter on sets, the geometry and measurement chapter of the teacher's guide hardly provides guidance about how the teaching would relate to the Ethiopian culture. The chapter provides a list of suggestions for teaching aids. The list does not contain any of the traditional instruments or artifacts in the Ethiopian culture. In its section about measurement there is no mention of the traditional ways of measuring.

A further look at activities

Here I attempt to investigate some of the activities further. In the shopping task, the activity of shopping is external to the schooling activity. In the schooling activity, a story about another activity is presented to engage students in mathematics task. The students do not have access to the shopping activity while engaging in the task. Nevertheless, it is likely that students already have the experience in participating in the activity of shopping. A reiteration of this external activity is used as a mediating artefact in the schooling activity. The textbook does not suggest providing an opportunity of some form of participation in the activity (cf. Miettinen, 1999). According to Miettinen (1999), actual participation in the activity than being presented about the activity results in better learning.

In a similar way, the textbook presents about the activity of restaurant. This activity involves the production and service of Ethiopian dishes, a cultural product. There are division of labor, rules and instruments of the production. However, they are not the focus of the task. The focus is only on the list of dishes. As mentioned earlier in this section, there are few out-of-school activities mentioned in the textbook and the teacher's guide, some of which have cultural connection of mathematics. However, these activities are not fully exploited in a way that gives the students the opportunity to participate and have a role in the activities. They are just presented with the story of the activities. In the schooling activity, these external activities are not presented in an engaging way. The teacher's guide hardly gives guidance on the issue of cultural connection. Suggestions of possible cultural communities to which the student belongs are scarce. It states that the teacher is encouraged to use out-of-school activities. However, it rarely mentions the out-of-school activities, which are embedded in the Ethiopian culture.

The textbook and the teacher's guide expose about the schooling activity in many ways. They determine the school rule and the classroom norms since they inform what is the right way to behave in the mathematics classroom and what rules to follow in the teaching and

learning of mathematics. They determine the division of labor by informing what the mathematics teacher and learner should do. The student uses the textbook in learning mathematics and the teacher gives homework from the textbook. Thus, the textbook is an instrument, which mediates learning mathematics. The textbook and the teacher's guide inform the teacher's decision of forming working groups in the classroom (school communities) or conceptions of school communities. It can also influence the teacher's perceptions of out-of-school activities. Another instrument, which mediates learning mathematics, is language. As mentioned earlier, the textbook presents mathematics in the students own languages. On the other hand, clarity of the use of terms in the language can promote or hinder their learning of mathematics.

Discussion

The results expose the limitations of the mathematics textbook and the teacher's guide in fostering learning mathematics with a cultural connection. The available literature suggests the possibilities as well as the advantages of making cultural connections (Jannok Nutti, 2013, Fyhn et al., 2017, Lipka & Adams, 2004). Besides earlier studies undertaken in Ethiopia also expose the potential cultural resources, which could avail themselves for the teaching of mathematics (Dutton, 1968; Gebremichael et al., 2011).

It was set out in introduction that studies undertaken about indigenous cultures show that the cultural activities and artefacts provide learning opportunities for the child. For example, in the production of braiding, which is a cultural and historically situated activity in the Sámi culture, children and elders take different roles. There are rules of the process as well as for the interaction, children have to listen and follow what parents/elders tell and do. The object of the activity includes the goals and motives. The goals for engaging the child in the process is transferring cultural knowledge and the motive for producing such artifacts is preserving the Sámi culture. The outcomes of the activity are the braiding and the child with a skill of making a braiding. As set out earlier in the introduction, earlier studies show that the Ethiopian context is also favorable for making cultural connection. It provides similar opportunities of diverse activities, which are parts of the various cultures in Ethiopia. These activities have own communities and involve rules, division of labor, instruments, and artefacts.

The textbook and teacher's guide do not suggest providing an opportunity of some form of participation in the activities (cf. Miettinen, 1999). Contrary to the suggestion by Miettinen the teaching materials stress motivation for the sake of mastery and succeeding in examinations instead of interest in engaging in culturally connected mathematics. I stated in the data presentation and analysis that the policy document objectively claims that it will provide education which is secular. It appears that the teaching materials almost ignored local contexts partly in the name of secularism.

Earlier studies in Ethiopia revealed that students of upper secondary were able to name several traditional activities which are inherent in the Ethiopian society where they tell about the utilization of elementary mathematics (Gebremichael et al., 2011). Given that the

teacher's guide provides detailed guidance about what the teacher should do in every topic, the absence of guidance on the issue of cultural connection is likely to hamper the teacher's actions in this respect. Another issue is language. Though students learn mathematics, using textbook, which is in their own language, description of some of the mathematics terms are not provided, which can hinder their learning (cf. Setati, 2005). For Setati part of learning mathematics is mastery of its language.

Concluding remarks

The educational policy document appears to influence textbook and the teacher's guide as the guiding documents in isolating the mathematics classroom from the local culture. Children need not be disconnected from their cultural heritages so that they can succeed at school. Lipka and Adams (2004) suggest otherwise. According to Lipka and Adams, mathematics education of children of indigenous communities need to be connected to their cultural heritages so that the children can succeed at school. As the studies show it, the issue of cultural connection in mathematics should not be seen as a dichotomy between developing children's knowledge of mathematics based on the local culture or developing knowledge of the standard mathematics. As Jannok Nutti (2013) puts it, it should rather be seen as uniting the two, with a due regard for the importance of both.

There should be more focus on cultural connection in mathematics, which is based on the diverse culture in Ethiopia. It is important that teaching resources with cultural connections are available for the teachers including guidance about how they can use these materials. The textbook is in students' own language. This is important for their learning. However, there are limitations in the textbook in that some terms are not described, which may affect their learning of topics.

The data analysis shows that the textbook and the teacher's guide would tell us most of what would happen in the mathematics classroom. However, it remains to undertake a study into the implementation of the mathematics curriculum using the textbook.

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Supplements

Supplement 1

5.2 ውቅሮች

በዚህ ርዕስ ስር ስለውቅሮች ትማራለህ/ሽ። ከዚህም ሌላ ነጥቦችን እንዴት የውቅር ወለሎች ላይ በስርጥ ጥንድ ቅደም ተከተል መግለፅ እንደምትችል/ዩ ትማራለህ/ሽ።

Supplement 2

ሀ. በደብተርህ/ሽ ላይ ሁለት ቀጠ-ዘዌ መስመር የሆኑትን ስራ/ሪ።

Supplement 3

የስብስብን ትርጉም ከመስጠትህ/ሽ በፊት የተለያዩ ምሳሌዎችን በተማሪው መጽሐፍ መግቢያ ላይ ከተሰጡት ጋር የሚመሳሰሉትን ግለጽላቸው። ይህም ተማሪዎቹ የስብስብ ዕንሰ ሀሳብ እንዲረዱ እና እንዲማሩ ይረዳቸዋል። ከዚህም ሌላ ይህ በዕለታዊ ኑሮአቸው ውስጥ የሚገኙ የነገሮችን ስብስብ እና በሒሳብ ትምህርት ውስጥ የሚገኝ ስብስብ አንድ ላይ እንዲያጣምሩ ይረዳቸዋል። ማብራሪያህን በአከባቢ የሚገኙትን ነገሮች ስብስብ የጋራ ስም ካላቸው ከታች ከተሰጡት መጀመር ትችላለህ/ሽ።

- ♣ «ቤተሰብ» የሰዎች ስብስብ «ልጆች እና ቤተሰቦቻቸው»።
- ♣ «ክፍል» በክፍልህ ውስጥ ያሉ የተማሪዎች ስብስብ።
- ♣ «ቡድን» የእግር ኳስ ተጫዋቾች ስብስብ እና የመሳሰሉት።

ለዚህ ጉዳይ ትግበራ 1.1 ምሳሌ 1 እና በተማሪው መማሪያ ውስጥ የተሰጡትን የቡድን ሥራ 1.1 ጥያቄዎችን መጠቀም ትችላለህ/ሽ። የምትጠቀምባቸው ምሳሌዎች እና ተጨባጭ ነገሮች ለሁሉም ተማሪዎች ግልፅ(ሁሉም ተማሪዎች የሚረዱት) መሆን አለበት።ተማሪዎቹ በሚደረገው ውይይት ውስጥ እንዲሳተፉ አበረታታቸው። ተማሪዎቹ የስብስብን ምንነት በዕለት ኑሮዎቸው ውስጥ የሚገኝ እና በሒሳብ ትምህርት ውስጥ የራሳቸውን ምሳሌ እንዲሰጡ አበረታታቸው።

Supplement 4

8 እግሮች ያሉዎቸው ድመቶች ስብስብ።

Supplement 5

ከተማሪው መጽሐፍ ምሳሌ 40 እና መ ተመሪዎቹ እንዲወያዩበት አድርግ/ጊ።
በመቀጠል ተማሪዎቹ የአላቅ ስብስብ ምሳሌ ያልሆነውን እንዲሰሩ ጠይቅ/ቂ።
ከመልመጃ 1.2 ውስጥ በ5ኛ ጥያቄ ላይ ተማሪዎች እንዲወያዩበት በማድረግ አላቅ ስብስብ እና አልቆ-ቢሰ ስብስብ እንዲለዩ እርዳቸው/ጂያቸው።

ግምገማ

ከመልመጃ 1.2 ውስጥ የቀሩትን ጥያቄዎች ለተማሪዎቹ የቤት ሥራ በመስጠት ስራቸውን ገምግሙ።

የቡድን ሥራ 1.2 መልስ

ሀ እና ሐ ባዶ ስብስብ ናቸው።

የትግበራ 1.1 መልስ

1. የተማሪዎች ቡድን፣ የእግር ኳስ ተጨዋቾች ቡድን፣ የዶሮዎች ስብስብ፣ ሁለት ሰልፍ የተማሪዎች ስብስብ።
2. እግር ኳስ የሚጫወቱ ሰዎች።
3. የ 9 ዶሮዎች ስብስብ።